

Sample Name: dNTPs ATP mix 2.5uM

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Acq. Operator   : SYSTEM                      Seq. Line :    1
Sample Operator : SYSTEM
Acq. Instrument : HPLC-UV-FC                 Location  :    1
Injection Date  : 12/10/2020 12:22:00 PM     Inj       :    1
                                           Inj Volume: 50.000 µl
Method          : C:\Users\Public\Documents\ChemStation\3\Data\dNMP to dNTP yield 2020-12-10
                  12-20-56\dNTP QUANTIFICATION.M (Sequence Method)
Last changed    : 12/10/2020 10:10:22 AM by SYSTEM
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Fraction Information
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No Fractions found.
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Area Percent Report
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Sorted By      :      Signal
Multiplier     :      1.0000
Dilution       :      1.0000
Do not use Multiplier & Dilution Factor with ISTDs

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Signal 1: VWD1 A, Wavelength=254 nm

Peak #	RetTime [min]	Type	Width [min]	Area [mAU*s]	Height [mAU]	Area %
1	10.575	BB	0.1875	91.34373	7.48396	11.9456
2	13.004	BB	0.1729	181.18158	16.35684	23.6942
3	14.854	BB	0.1789	96.19533	8.30269	12.5801
4	16.304	BB	0.1793	205.49913	17.67732	26.8744
5	18.456	BB	0.1848	190.44534	15.90329	24.9057

